

THE LITERARY SOURCES OF THE “LAYLI AND MAJNUN” NARRATIVE POEMS

Turdiyeva Maftuna Abdurahmonovna

Lecturer at the Uzbek state university of world languages, PhD

maftuna1991tur@gmail.com

Abstract. In Eastern literature, in particular, in epic poetry, the development of the theme of Layla and Majnun and its inherent guiding principles were manifested in the epics “Layla and Majnun”, created within the framework of the tradition of khamsanavisi. It is necessary to recognize that literary sources were important factor in the emergence of the tradition of writing works on this topic. The article analyzes information on the genesis of the images of Layla and Majnun based on the source of the poet scholar Abul Faraj Isfahani.

Key words: Abul Faraj Isfahani, source, epic, image, Qays, Majnun, Layla.

Introduction. The various compilations and literary collections containing different versions of the story of Layli and Majnun laid the foundation for the formation of the dominant tendencies that later became the basis of narrative poems on this theme and contributed to the emergence of works bearing the same title but offering distinct interpretations. In this regard, three primary sources deserve special attention. Ibn Qutaybah’s *Kitāb al-Shi‘r wa al-Shu‘arā’* is particularly valuable due to its relatively early date (9th century), which is closer to the period traditionally associated with the lives of Layli and Majnun (7th century). Abū al-Faraj al-Iṣfahānī’s *Kitāb al-Aghānī* (“The Book of Songs”) is distinguished by the comprehensiveness of its information, while Abū Bakr al-Walībī’s *Dīwān Majnūn wa Laylā* is significant because it was compiled shortly before the creation of Niẓāmī Ganjavī’s *Layli and Majnun* (1188), namely in the eleventh–twelfth centuries. It may be assumed that al-Iṣfahānī’s *Kitāb al-Aghānī* also served as an important literary source for Niẓāmī Ganjavī, the first poet to compose a *Khamsa* and the author of the earliest surviving poetic version of *Layli and Majnun*. Sources indicate that Niẓāmī consulted ancient Arabic, Persian, Armenian, and Greek texts while composing his poem [3, 14]. Selecting from these sources those episodes that he considered most suitable for his narrative, he created a new plot structure and artistically reorganized diverse, and sometimes contradictory, accounts through an original compositional design. This principle subsequently became a model for later versions of *Layli and Majnun*.

Main Part. The *Book of Songs* by the Arab literary scholar Abū al-Faraj al-Iṣfahānī (897–967) may be regarded as one of the earliest sources in which the name Qays appears. The work contains information about poets and singers from the earliest period of Arab musical culture, spanning from the pre-Islamic era and the seventh century up to the author’s own time in the ninth century. The *Book of Songs* introduces numerous narratives concerning Majnun. Regarding the work and its author, Ignaty Krachkovsky notes in his article “*The Early History of the Tale of Majnun and Layla in Arabic Literature*”:

“He does not follow the conventional chronology of history: events from the earlier period of Majnun’s life often appear after later events; genealogical and other information is intermixed with reports concerning Majnun and the events of his life and is introduced without any systematic plan. Despite possessing a considerable amount of material from earlier sources, al-Iṣfahānī made no attempt to transform it into a coherent chain of narratives” [6, 493].

Nevertheless, al-Iṣfahānī’s *Book of Songs* remains valuable because it preserves testimonies from several historians and scholars concerning Majnun and the question of his historical existence. Although some of these accounts contradict one another, by selecting those that are mutually consistent and correspond to the narrative framework of the story, it becomes possible to reconstruct an image of Majnun as the protagonist of the tale.

It is well known that the *Layli and Majnun* poems of Nizāmī Ganjavī and Alisher Navoi begin with the motif of childlessness. The motifs of childlessness and supplication to God for a child found in these works do not appear to originate from Arabic sources but rather from oral folklore traditions and ancient epic narratives. In the extant literary sources devoted to the story, there is no mention that Qays was a long-awaited or divinely granted child. On the contrary, al-İşfahānī's *Book of Songs* provides the following account:

“Aḥmad ibn ‘Abd al-‘Azīz and Ḥabīb ibn Naşr related to us through ‘Umar ibn Shabba, who heard it from al-Haytham ibn ‘Adī, who in turn transmitted it from ‘Uthmān ibn ‘Umāra ibn Ḥarīm al-Murrī: ‘I travelled to the land of Banū ‘Āmir hoping to meet Majnun. They showed me where he lived. When I arrived, I found his father, already advanced in age, surrounded by many of his children. I asked them about Majnun. They began to weep. The old man said: By God, he was dearer to me than all of these standing here. He fell in love with a girl from his tribe. She was not worthy even of Majnun’s aspirations. However, after their love became known, the girl’s father refused to marry her to him and instead gave her to another man” [11].

Abdurahman Jami, who sought to adhere closely to the Arabic narrative tradition in composing his own *Layli and Majnun*, reflects a similar family structure. In Jami’s version, Qays is the twelfth and most beloved child of his father. The statement in the *Book of Songs* that “the girl was not worthy even of Majnun’s aspirations” appears to have inspired the episode in Jami’s poem in which Qays’s father considers Layli’s family socially unsuitable for his son. In contrast, neither the earlier poets nor Navoi depict such an attitude; rather, Layli’s family is said to reject Qays because of his madness.

According to the *Book of Songs*, after Qays persisted in his love, his parents were compelled to ask for Layli’s hand in marriage. The source relates:

“Majnun’s father, mother, and the men of his tribe went to Layla’s father. They advised him and implored him in the name of God and kinship: ‘This young man stands on the brink of destruction and is losing his reason. Do not bring calamity upon his father and family. We beseech you in God’s name—do not do this.’ They continued: ‘The girl is not more noble than Majnun, nor do you possess wealth comparable to that of his father. He leaves the amount of the marriage gift entirely to your discretion and is prepared to give all his property if necessary. We ask only that you consent.’ Yet Layla’s father firmly refused.”

After this refusal, Layli was immediately married to another man from her tribe. Upon hearing the news, Majnun lost all hope and became insane. Members of the tribe advised his father to take him to the Ka‘ba and pray for deliverance from this affliction. During the pilgrimage, when they reached a place called Tan‘īm, someone cried out, “O Layla!” Hearing this, Majnun collapsed unconscious. When he finally regained consciousness, he recited verses whose meaning was: “O God, increase my love for Layla!” [11].

In the poems of Nizāmī and Navoi, this episode was artistically transformed and further developed. Instead of hearing Layli’s name, Majnun himself prays at the Ka‘ba that God may intensify his love for Layli, after which he loses consciousness.

The information about Majnun in Ibn Qutaybah’s *Kitāb al-Shi‘r wa al-Shu‘arā’* indicates that he and Layli tended sheep together in childhood; al-İşfahānī’s *Book of Songs* refers more generally to livestock, while the *Dīwān Majnūn wa Laylā* specifically mentions sheep [8, 11]. Layli is described as being well acquainted with poetry and literature and as enjoying the company of the young men of Banū ‘Āmir, among whom Majnun was her closest companion. When the youths realized that Layli and Majnun had fallen in love, they informed Layli’s father [8, 11].

A similar account appears in Ibn Qutaybah’s work:

“Majnun and Layli fell in love while tending sheep together during childhood. Majnun grew into a handsome young man, a pleasant conversationalist, and a renowned poet. He continued to converse with Layli and her relatives” [8, 11].

This suggests that the two young people developed affection for one another through literary conversations while tending their flocks. As they matured and their poetic talents developed, they began exchanging verses, and their love deepened. Eventually they joined the social gatherings of young men and women within the tribe. Al-İşfahānī describes one such gathering:

“Majnun sat in an assembly where the girl was present among a group of young men. He was the most handsome and graceful among them and recited Arabic poetry more beautifully than anyone else. Whenever he spoke, the gathering came alive. The girl did not look at him directly and instead turned toward others. Yet the same fire that burned in Majnun’s heart had entered hers as well. She sensed what was in his heart but did not fully trust her intuition” [11].

One day Layli expressed her feelings in verse:

I saw traces of sorrow in your eyes;
If you burn with love, I burn as well.
I too am in love with you—my heart knows it.
Both of us are known among people for virtue and excellence.
Each of us is a friend upon whom the other may rely [11].

Reworking this episode, the great authors Nizāmī, Amīr Khusraw Dehlavī, and Navoi presented the love story in a new form. The social gathering became a school environment. Majnun’s qualities—his beauty, grace, and mastery of poetry—were supplemented by intellectual brilliance and learning. The statement that “the girl sensed what was in Majnun’s heart but did not fully trust it” was expanded by Navoi into the episode of Layli’s garden excursion, through which she seeks to clarify Qays’s feelings. Such a scene is absent from earlier sources. Likewise, the report that Layli once expressed her feelings in poetry was transformed by Navoi into a scene in which Layli, noticing Majnun’s sorrow, asks him about his condition while walking in the garden.

The content of Layli’s poem cited in the *Book of Songs* demonstrates that both Layli and Majnun were regarded as young people distinguished by virtue and accomplishment. This aspect was emphasized and further developed by Nizāmī and Navoi. In their poems, both protagonists are portrayed as educated, intellectually refined, and poetically gifted individuals.

Conclusion. The origins of the Layli and Majnun theme can be traced back to ancient Arabic sources. Among the earliest and most significant of these is Abū al-Faraj al-İşfahānī’s *Kitāb al-Aghānī (The Book of Songs)*. Knowledge of the information concerning Layli and Majnun preserved in this source is important because it enables scholars to identify the literary influences that shaped the evolution of later narrative poems on the theme, as well as the development of their plots, motifs, characters, and ideological features.

REFERENCES:

1. Navoi, Alisher. *Layli and Majnun*. Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 2006.
2. Jami, Abdurahman. *Layli and Majnun*. Translated by O. Bo‘riyev. Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1989.
3. Aliyev, G. *Themes and Plots of Nizami in the Literatures of the Peoples of the East*. Moscow, 1985.
4. Bertels, E. E. *Navoi: A Monograph*. Translated from Russian by I. Mirzayev. Tashkent: Tafakkur qanoti, 2015.
5. Жамматова М. “Ранние источники дастана “Лейли и Меджнун” // Актуальные проблемы тюркологии: Россия и тюрко-мусульманский мир. Материалы международной тюркологической конференции. — Казань. 2021. — 493 с.
6. Крачковский И.Ю. Том II. Избранные соч. — Москва-Ленинград: Наука, 1956.

7. Kudelin A. Arabic literature: Poetics and stylistics. Manuscripta Orientalia. Vol 10.N 2. \June. 2004.
8. Nizami Ganjavi. *Layli and Majnun*. Translated by Jamol Kamol. Tashkent: Extremum-Press, 2017.
9. Khodjayeva, Ra'no. *The Genre System and Typology of Classical Arabic Literature: A Monograph*. Tashkent, 2015.
10. <https://islamicbook.ws/adab/alagani-002.html> (2022)